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Spender Tax Plan

Allegra Spender has put forward an interesting tax reform package, *Personal Tax White Paper*. At its core the paper seeks a revenue-neutral tax mix switch by “reducing taxes on income from labour, and increasing taxes on income from assets”.¹ The paper has a predominantly equity framework, seeking to enhance intergenerational equity by helping young people achieve financial security.²

While one may quibble with some aspects of the plan (which I do below), on the whole it amounts to a ‘broaden the base, lower the rate’ income tax reform package, and has much to commend it.

Personal Income Tax Cuts

The centrepiece of the proposed decrease in taxation of labour income is a reduction in the bottom personal income tax (PIT) marginal tax rate (MTR) to 13% and a 2.5pp cut in the other MTRs. This goes further than the government’s current PIT rate cuts which reduce the bottom MTR to 14%. The paper contemplates indexing the PIT thresholds for inflation, but opts instead for the rate cuts because that would provide more support for wage earners now.³

Indexation of the tax rate thresholds is a way to automatically counter the bracket creep effects inherent in a progressive rate structure. Bracket creep occurs because with the tax rate thresholds legislated in nominal terms, increases in individuals’ wages over time push them onto higher average (and sometimes marginal) tax rates.

Governments regularly announce ‘tax cuts’, which in effect just return the effects of this bracket creep. Indeed, the PIT share of total Commonwealth tax revenue has been fairly constant at around half for 50 years. What’s more, the progressivity of the PIT rate scale has also not changed significantly over that time. That is, governments have consistently returned bracket creep, not just in aggregate, but to the very income groups they got it from.⁴

The government’s current legislated PIT cuts will broadly maintain that situation. Chart 1 shows that, taking 2012-13 as a base year, the average tax rate (ATR) schedule in 2027-28 will be similar to what it would have been if the tax thresholds had been indexed for inflation since 2012-13.⁵

¹ Spender p. 5.

² Spender, p. 32.

³ Spender, p. 8.

⁴ See my paper *Progressivity of Individuals Income Tax in Australia: Long-term Trends*, TTPI Working Paper No. 9, 2025 [Here](#)

⁵ My paper *Stage 3 Tax Cuts v Bracket Creep: Time to Index the Personal Income Tax Rate Scale* sets out this methodology [Here](#)

Chart 1: Government Legislated Personal Income Tax Scale versus Indexation

Source: Author calculations

The Spender proposed PIT cuts go further, producing lower ATRs for most taxpayers than they would have been if the tax thresholds had been indexed since 2012-13 (see Chart 2). The biggest winners on this metric are mid-high-income earners. It is important to note, though, that this is the group that would be most heavily affected by the base-broadening measures in the package.

Chart 2: Spender Proposed Personal Income Tax Scale versus Indexation

Source: Author calculations

Overall, the paper’s proposed PIT cuts would achieve their objective of lowering tax rates for mid- to high-income earners, with this group most affected by the base-broadening measures.⁶ That said, this group is relatively unresponsive to modest changes in tax rates, with the obligations and lack of flexibility of full-time workers mitigating against changes in hours worked. Higher responsiveness to tax changes is likely with lower-income earners, in particular part-time secondary-income earners.

⁶ See discussion at Spender, 4.2.4, p. 35.

Taxation of Earnings

The revenue to pay for the PIT cuts is proposed to come from increases in the taxation of certain forms of capital income. On one view, this would create a non-neutrality, as capital income is generally more price elastic than labour income. However, the capital income in question is mainly from domestic savings which is not as elastic as foreign capital operating in international markets.

The paper appears to adopt an income tax benchmark for its analysis, with departures from this seen as concessions. An alternative expenditure tax benchmark would exempt the returns from savings to prevent the so-called 'double taxation' of savings. Income = consumption + savings. So, the difference between income and expenditure (consumption) tax benchmark is savings. Hence, the tax treatment of savings is where the thorniest tax policy issues typically lie.

As a reference point, the government's *Tax Expenditures and Insights Statement* uses an income tax benchmark (Haig-Simos) as a starting point for its benchmark for measuring tax expenditures. This drives the large measured tax expenditures for the main forms of savings, ie owner-occupied housing and superannuation, which are taxed more in line with an expenditure tax benchmark.

Without going further into the income versus expenditure benchmark debate, it can be noted that with the partial taxation of most forms of savings, the Australian tax system is actually a hybrid of the two. The more important policy objective, for both equity and efficiency purposes, is to have consistency of tax treatment across different forms of savings. Or, put the other way, to note that the lack of consistency in the taxation of savings in Australia is a problem.⁷ See Chart 3.

Chart 3: Effective Tax Rates by Savings Vehicles

Source: *Re:Think: Tax Discussion Paper*, p. 60, March 2015. For individuals with MTR = 32.5%.

Minimum Tax Rate for Non-Labour Income

The paper suggests a partial schedular approach to the taxation of investment income generally, with a minimum tax rate of 27.5%. The main purpose of the measure, other than revenue raising, appears to be tackling the use of family trusts to artificially split income to access lower tax rates. While this would be a blunt measure to tackle the abuses with the use of trusts for tax avoidance purposes, the apparent lack of effective alternatives gives it some appeal.

⁷ See my paper *Is Haig-Simons Still Relevant to Tax Reform in Australia?* JAT, Vol 27, Issue 2, 2025 [Here](#)

Capital Gains Tax

The proposed reduction in the capital gains tax (CGT) discount from 50% to 30% is justified mainly as a revenue-raiser to help pay for the PIT reductions.⁸ Under an income tax approach, real capital gains should be taxed, but an allowance should be made to remove the inflation component.⁹ That was the approach when the CGT was introduced in 1985, with the cost base being indexed by the Consumer Price Index (CPI). In 1999 this indexation approach was replaced with the current 50% discount, both as a simplification measure and to provide a deliberate incentive to investment.¹⁰

The Henry review considered this issue and concluded that a 40% discount would be more consistent with a long-term on-average inflation adjustment.¹¹ Importantly, to enhance consistency this approach was also proposed for other savings vehicles, in particular interest and the net income of rental properties (ie, rent on the income side and interest etc. on the expense side).

The paper's proposed 30% CGT discount is probably an inadequate inflation adjustment. That said, the exact discount chosen matters less than consistency across savings vehicles, including addressing the asymmetry in the tax treatment of the income and expenses sides of investments.

Negative Gearing

The paper proposes ring-fencing investment income deductions, not allowing net losses to be combined with labour income. While acknowledging this would increase the taxation of housing, hence reducing incentives to build and increasing rents, it nevertheless claims these effects would be small, and outweighed by the upsides of additional revenue for PIT cuts and increasing home ownership.

I found this to be the conceptually weakest part of the paper, which at one point asserts that arguing such tax increases would lead landlords to raise rents, running counter to basic economic theory.¹² A perplexing claim, given that the economic incidence of tax changes is generally considered to be shared between suppliers and consumers depending on their price elasticities, and in the face of the subsequent acknowledgement that there would be such effects, albeit small.¹³

I see the case for some reduction in the CGT discount to better reflect an adjustment for inflation. If long-term asset price growth was 6% and inflation 2.5%, a 40 % discount (as proposed in Henry) would be in the right ballpark. A superior approach would be a return to the pre-1999 indexation. Even more important would be to achieve greater consistency and symmetry in the taxation of different investments, along the lines of the Henry review proposal discussed above.

I find it more difficult to accept the assertion that negative gearing is a tax concession. Clearly there is an asymmetry in the taxation of rental properties, with full nominal tax deductions on the expense side, but less than full inclusion of income (full taxation of rental income, but partial CGT). The point, though, is that to the extent there is a departure from a full income tax approach, it is on the income side with the CGT treatment, not on the expenses side with the deductibility of interest. Crucially, the

⁸ Spender, p. 47.

⁹ Ideally gains would be taxed as they accrue, but practical and political challenges have prevented that, leaving a concessional element in the CGT treatment.

¹⁰ The government policy statement referred to the need to "stimulate greater participation by individuals in investment". See Peter Costello, *The New Business Tax System*, Attachment D, p2, 21 September 1999.

¹¹ Henry et al, Part 2, Volume 1, p. 72

¹² Spender, p. 48.

¹³ Spender, p. 49.

CGT discount is the same for investments whether they are negatively geared or not. We are simply barking up the wrong tree with the focus on negative gearing.¹⁴

Another crucial aspect of the taxation of housing debate (strangely absent from the paper) is the tax treatment of owner-occupied housing. In contrast to rental properties, it is fully exempt from income tax, fully exempt from CGT, exempt from land tax and largely excluded from the age pension asset means test. In the debate around the taxation of rental properties, it seems to get lost that it is generally lower-income people in rental properties and generally higher-income people in owner-occupied properties. Surely the last thing we should be doing is skewing the tax system even further in favour of the latter group.

Overall, in regard to the proposed capital income tax changes the paper argues that the negative economic effects should be small, with tax arrangements more relevant to the composition of investment than the overall level.¹⁵ This seems reasonable. But it should also be noted that the proposed reductions in PIT that are skewed to mid-high-income earners will also have little economic effect. In short, in regard to economic growth, it looks like a nil-all draw.

Superannuation Tax Reform

My personal favourite part of the paper is the proposed change to make the taxation of earnings in superannuation funds more progressive. The paper makes the strong point that “Superannuation tax settings are unlikely to be stable unless they are fair.”¹⁶ There are good arguments for taxing superannuation concessional compared to a full nominal income tax benchmark, but the lack of effective progressivity is fundamentally inequitable.

The taxation of contributions to superannuation funds has been made more progressive with the addition of the Low-Income Super Tax Offset (LISTO) and Division 293 (see Chart 4). But, the flat tax rate approach to the taxation of earnings continues to favour higher-income individuals and provide a strong incentive for them to invest heavily in superannuation, way beyond retirement income needs. The complex array of caps we have is necessary to contain the extent to which high-income earners exploit this tax concession.

Chart 4: Taxation of Superannuation Contributions versus Personal Income Tax Rates

Note: PIT scale includes LITO and ML. Super scale includes LISTO and Div 293.

¹⁴ See my paper *Negative Gearing: Is It A Tax Concession?* TTPi Policy Brief, No. 6, 2024 [Here](#)

¹⁵ Spender, p. 8.

¹⁶ Spender, p. 57.

The paper proposes to tax superannuation earnings in the retirement phase more progressively with stepped increases in the MTR on earnings as balances increase (a variant of the government's recently legislated measure). The stated aim is to have MTRs on earnings that are 12.5pp below the PIT MTRs that apply outside super (assuming a 6% rate of return).¹⁷

This proposal is a step on from the Henry review proposal to tax superannuation contributions at PIT MTRs minus a flat rebate, so everyone gets the same tax rate reduction. These approaches are conceptually appealing in delivering a level of progressivity in the taxation of superannuation that reflects that outside superannuation, while providing a uniform level of concessionality to all.

The challenge for these approaches in the past has been their administrability. Advances in tax administration and data management, though, have made that less an issue – as indicated by the government's recent measure. Taking this a step further, if it were possible to match an individual's superannuation income with their income outside superannuation, then their PIT MTRs (minus a flat rebate) could be directly applied to their superannuation earnings (and contributions).

Superannuation Guarantee

There is also a lifetime equity aspect to these issues. Young people become old people, so some of the issues are intragenerational rather than intergenerational.¹⁸

The paper does not directly address Australia's Superannuation Guarantee (SG) arrangements which require 12% of wages to be contributed to superannuation, ie a compulsory deferral of income from when we are younger and working to when we are older and retired. In our 3-pillar retirement income system, an SG rate of around 10% would achieve the OECD benchmark of a 2/3 replacement rate for median earners to maintain living standards in retirement. 12% may be skewing things too far in favour of our older selves.

Conclusion

Overall, this paper makes an interesting and important contribution to the tax reform debate in Australia. It makes it harder for the government to ignore the imperative for tax reform.

¹⁷ Spender, p. 58 (see Figure 25).

¹⁸ See discussion in Varela et al, *Measuring the Changing Size of Intergenerational Transfers in the Australian Tax and Transfer System*, TTPI Working Paper 7, 2025 [Here](#)